

FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF ANTONYMS IN TURKISH AND AZERBAIJANI PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: The article provides a comparative analysis of the semantic and stylistic features of antonyms in Turkish and Azerbaijani proverbs. The study demonstrates that antonyms in paremiological texts are not used solely to create opposition; they also perform functions such as comparison, generalization, enumeration, and figurative representation. The structural realization and syntactic positioning of antonyms in proverbs enhance the expressive force of the text and contribute to the more vivid transmission of folk wisdom.

The analysis reveals that some antonymic pairs gradually lose their original oppositional meaning over time and develop into stable semantic units with generalized meanings. The comparison of Turkish and Azerbaijani paremiological examples shows that antonyms play an important role in expressing life experiences, human relations, and moral values in both languages. At the same time, similar semantic patterns are realized through different images and expressive means shaped by distinct national and cultural contexts.

Keywords: paremiological units, antonymy, semantic features, pragmatic functions, Turkish and Azerbaijani proverbs

Antonyms occupy a significant position in the semantic structure and stylistic organization of proverbs. The juxtaposition of lexemes with opposing meanings contributes to a more expressive, memorable, and emotionally marked presentation of ideas. In paremiological units, which reflect the product of collective folk cognition and cultural experience, antonymic relations serve to generalize human behavior, life experience, and social observations. In this regard, antonyms function not merely as stylistic devices, but also as essential lexical-semantic components involved in the formation of the semantic framework of the paremiological text.

The paremia “Öfkeyle kalkan zararlı oturur” (“He who acts in anger ends up in loss”) [4, p.261] is semantically based on the idea that anger and emotionally driven decisions lead to negative consequences. In this example, the antonymic relation between the verbs “kalkmak” (to rise) and “oturmak” (to sit) creates a contrast between the beginning and the outcome of the action, thereby enhancing the expressive effect of the statement. Although certain components of the paremia may be modified to some extent, the semantic and stylistic force of the expression weakens when the antonymic opposition established by these verbs is not preserved. It is precisely through this contrast that the consequences of human behavior are conveyed in a figurative and expressive manner.

A similar feature can also be observed in the paremia “Alim olmaq asandır, adam olmaq çətin” (“It is easy to become a scholar, but difficult to become a true human being”) [2, p.53]. In this example, the antonyms “asan” (easy) and “çətin” (difficult) create a contrast between two different concepts, emphasizing the distinction between acquiring knowledge and attaining moral maturity. The semantic opposition established by these antonyms allows the proverbial wisdom to be expressed more vividly and increases the didactic effect of the paremia. Such examples demonstrate that antonyms in paremiological units perform not only a contrastive function, but also reflect the people’s worldview and their perception of human character and life values.

The functioning of antonyms within the paremiological system is not confined merely to the creation of lexical opposition. In proverbs and other paremiological units shaped through folk tradition, antonymic relations contribute both to the formation of semantic cohesion and to the emotionally expressive realization of meaning. By means of oppositional lexical elements, human character, social relations, life phenomena, and moral values are represented through comparative and contrastive perspectives. Consequently, antonyms in paremiological texts operate not only as stylistic devices, but also as significant linguistic components that constitute the internal semantic organization of the text.

The use of antonyms in proverbs is also associated with the people's tendency to perceive the world through binary oppositions. Through the comparison of contrasting poles such as good and evil, white and black, and right and wrong, life experience is generalized and certain conclusions are drawn. Such oppositions not only intensify the emotional impact of the text, but also facilitate the clearer and more memorable expression of proverbial wisdom. From this perspective, antonyms in paremiological units emerge as one of the linguistic means through which the collective worldview and folk cognition are expressed.

Syntactic Position and Expressive Function of Antonyms

The positional arrangement of antonyms within a paremiological text directly influences their semantic and stylistic functionality. The use of oppositional lexical units in close or distant syntactic positions determines the intensity of contrast and modifies the expressive potential of the text. When antonyms are employed in immediate proximity to one another, the opposition between them becomes relatively weakened, and the lexical units begin to function as a generalized semantic whole. This characteristic contributes both to the conciseness of paremiological texts and to the expansion of their semantic capacity.

In such paremiological examples as "Erenlerin sağı solu olmaz" ("A righteous person does not distinguish between right and left," referring to impartiality and spiritual integrity) [4, p.171], "İn kalk dünyası" ("The world is full of rises and falls," emphasizing the instability and cyclical nature of life) [4, p.209], "Axtaran tapar" ("He who seeks finds," expressing the idea that effort and persistence lead to success) [2, p.86], and "Al ver deyiblər, al vermə deməyiblər" ("People advise mutual exchange rather than one-sided possession," highlighting reciprocity in social relations) [1, p.26], antonymic lexical units are used in immediate proximity, thereby forming a unified semantic structure. Particularly in oppositional pairs such as "al-ver," the semantic emphasis is directed less toward contrast and more toward reciprocity and the natural course of life. Although the antonymic relation is not completely neutralized in such constructions, the dominant function shifts toward the expression of a generalized semantic meaning. Consequently, antonyms in these contexts serve not only as markers of opposition, but also as important components contributing to the semantic cohesion and integrity of paremiological discourse.

In the proverb "Dereyi tepəyi sel bilir, iyiyi kötüyü el bilir" ("The flood knows the valley and the hill, while people know who is good and who is bad") [4, p.150], the antonyms "iyi" (good) and "kötü" (bad) express the semantics of evaluation and differentiation. Here, the people's ability to distinguish between good and bad is presented in a generalized proverbial form. In the example "Sarmısak içli dişli, soğan yalnız başlı" ("Garlic consists of many cloves, whereas the onion has a single head") [4, p.272], the expression "içli-dişli" moves away from direct antonymic opposition and develops into a stable figurative unit characterizing a particular quality or feature. Such examples demonstrate that antonyms may, in certain contexts, move beyond their primary oppositional meaning and acquire new semantic qualities.

A similar feature can also be observed in the Azerbaijani paremia "Bərkdən-boşdan çıxmış adamdır" ("He is a person who has gone through various hardships and experiences in life") [2, p.117], where the combined use of antonymic elements gives rise to a generalized semantic meaning. In this expression, "bərkdən-boşdan" conveys the idea of passing through different difficulties and trials of life. Here, the antonymic components are not contrasted with one another; rather, together they form a stable semantic unit expressing human experience. The same characteristic is evident in

the example “Adam var, yaxşı-yamanı bilməz” (“There are people who cannot distinguish between good and bad”) [2, p.33]. In this context, the antonyms “yaxşı–yaman” denote not only positive and negative concepts, but also a more generalized meaning related to condition, situation, or circumstance. In the Azərbaycan dilinin izahlı lüğəti [3, vol.4, pp.510; 712], these expressions are recorded with meanings such as “state or condition,” “everything,” and “ordinary or acceptable.” This demonstrates that antonyms within the paremiological system may evolve into stable semantic models.

In examples where antonyms are positioned at a greater syntactic distance from one another, the contrast becomes more prominent and semantically intensified. The increase in syntactic distance strengthens the opposition between antonymic elements and enhances the emotional and expressive impact of the text. In the paremia “İki deliye bir uslu koymuşlar” (“Two foolish people are accompanied by one sensible person”) [4, p.206], the opposition between the words “deli” (foolish, irrational) and “uslu” (wise, sensible) clearly contrasts different models of human character and behavior. In the example “Ana tökəni bala yığar” (“What the mother wastes, the child gathers”) [2, p.60], the verbs “tökəni” (to scatter or waste) and “yığar” (to gather) create a semantic opposition between two contradictory actions.

In the proverb “Köçtük yurdun kadri konduk yurttā bilinir” (“The value of the homeland one leaves behind is understood only after settling in another place”) [4, p.185], the antonyms “köçtük” (left or departed) and “konduk” (settled) intensify the idea that people often realize the true value of a place only after separation from it. In the example “Yerin altını da bilir, üstünü də” (“He knows both the underground and the surface,” referring to a person with extensive knowledge and experience) [2, p.410], the antonyms “alt” (below) and “üst” (above) function as semantic devices expressing comprehensiveness and depth of knowledge. Such examples demonstrate that, as the syntactic distance between antonymic components increases, the expressive force of the contrast becomes more pronounced.

The comparative and characterizing function of antonyms

The juxtaposition of antonymic units performs an important function in the semantic structure of paremiological texts. The use of oppositional lexical items within the same context expands the possibilities of comparison and differentiation, thereby enabling a more comprehensive representation of objects, events, or human character. Such contrasts enhance both the semantic depth and the expressive force of proverbs.

In examples such as “Yırtıq böyük, yamaq kiçik” (“The tear is large, the patch is small”) [2, p.412], “Akın adı karanın tadı” (“The warrior’s name is like the taste of darkness/light,” emphasizing reputational contrast) [4, p.82], and “Alçak yerde yatma sel alır, yüksek yerde yatma yel alır” (“Do not lie in a low place, as the flood will take you; do not lie in a high place, as the wind will take you”) [4, p.84], antonymic units perform a comparative function. Through these oppositional lexical elements, the differences between events, conditions, and situations are presented more explicitly. In particular, the antonymic pair “alçak–yüksek” (low–high) generalizes a specific life experience on the basis of spatial opposition.

In some cases, antonymic oppositions serve to reveal different aspects of the same object or phenomenon. In the proverb “Ayın on beşi aydınlık, on beşi karanlıktır” (“Fifteen days of the month are bright, and fifteen are dark”) [4, p.106], the antonyms “aydınlık” (bright) and “karanlık” (dark) express the notion of variability and change. Here, the unstable and cyclical nature of life is represented through a natural phenomenon.

In the example “Ağ ayranı itə tökərlər, qara kişmiş cibə” (“White ayran is given to the dog, whereas black raisins are kept in the pocket”) [2, p.16], the antonyms “ağ” (white) and “qara” (black) function not only in a comparative sense but also in an evaluative one, highlighting a contrast in value and preference.

Antonyms also play a significant role in the characterization of human behavior and personality traits. In the proverb “Ağıllı qəm yeyər, dəli qəmçi” (“The wise endure sorrow, the foolish receive punishment”) [2, p.25], the antonyms “ağıllı” (wise) and “dəli” (foolish) establish a clear opposition

between different behavioral patterns. Thus, human attitudes toward life and modes of thinking are presented in a comparative framework, and the contrast between antonyms enhances the clarity and perceptibility of character distinctions.

In certain proverbs, one of the antonymic components serves to foreground the semantic salience of the other. In the example "Ağ evi görüb qara evi yandırmazlar" ("Having seen a white house, one does not burn the black house") [2, p.17], the opposition "ağ ev" (white house) and "qara ev" (black house) constructs a meaning based on choice and comparison. In the proverb "Ağ göyərçin qara qarğaya qismət olub" ("A white dove has fallen to the fate of a black crow") [2, p.17], the images "ağ göyərçin" (white dove) and "qara qarğa" (black crow) express aesthetic and moral contrasts. In "Körden gözlü, topaldan ayaklı, deliden deli" ("From the blind, sight; from the lame, walking; from the mad, madness") [4, p.241], the highlighting of certain traits is achieved through oppositional and contrastive relations.

In paremiological discourse, antonyms are also employed to enhance imagery and expressiveness. In the proverb "Ağacı çox olan kəndin məzarı az olar" ("A village with many trees has fewer graves") [2, p.21], the antonyms "çox" (many) and "az" (few) denote quantity but acquire a broader metaphorical meaning within the text, functioning as indicators of social well-being and living conditions. In "Güzel bürünür, çirkin görünür" ("The beautiful is covered, the ugly is revealed") [4, p.191], the antonyms "güzel" (beautiful) and "çirkin" (ugly) establish an evaluative opposition related to human appearance. In "Erkek sel, kadın göl" ("Man is a flood, woman is a lake") [4, p.172], the opposition between "erkek" (man) and "kadın" (woman) metaphorically expresses different character traits.

In the representation of moral qualities, the function of antonyms is particularly evident. In the proverb "Adam var rəhmət aparar, adam var lənət aparar" ("There are people who bring blessings, and there are people who bring curses") [2, p.33], the antonyms "rəhmət" (blessing) and "lənət" (curse) express the positive and negative evaluations formed about a person. Through this contrast, the moral imprint left by an individual in society is assessed. Such examples demonstrate that antonyms in the paremiological system function not only as lexical devices of opposition, but also as significant semantic means expressing the ethical and social values of folk thought.

The enumerative and generalizing function of antonyms

Antonymic units in paremiological texts do not function solely as means of establishing contrast; they also participate in the formation of enumerative and generalizing semantics. The paired use of oppositional lexical items enables the inclusion of different conceptual domains within a single textual structure, thereby expanding the overall semantic scope of the statement.

In the proverb "Ölüm var, dirim var" ("There is death, there is life") [4, p.263], the antonyms "ölüm" (death) and "dirim" (life) represent the two opposing poles of human existence; however, the primary aim is not merely to establish opposition. Rather, the expression conveys a generalized understanding of the wholeness of life and the different stages of human existence in an abstract and comprehensive manner. In the example "Adam var bir dost üçün qazanır, bir düşmən üçün" ("There are people who act for a friend and for an enemy") [2, p.35], the antonyms "dost" (friend) and "düşmən" (enemy) encompass different directions of social relations, thereby extending the meaning to a broader social and behavioral generalization.

The enumerative and generalizing function of antonyms

In the proverb "Al çevir, sat çevir, çaxçaxı qalsın sənə" ("Buy and turn it, sell and turn it, let the remainder be yours") [2, p.49], the antonyms "al" (buy) and "sat" (sell) express opposite directions of action and create an enumerative structure. In "Bir meşədə od düşsə, quru da yanar, yaş da" ("If a fire breaks out in a forest, both dry and green trees burn") [2, p.133], the antonyms "quru" (dry) and "yaş" (green/wet) demonstrate that objects in different conditions may be equally affected, thereby extending the meaning toward a generalizing conclusion about the scope of an event.

Antonyms in paremiological texts are also used to express characteristic features of humans, living beings, and various objects. In the proverb "Acın imanı olmaz, toxun amanı" ("The hungry has no faith, the satiated has no mercy") [2, p.92], the antonyms "ac" (hungry) and "tox" (satiated) reflect

the relationship between social condition and human behavior. In “Açılan solar, ağlayan gülər” (“What blooms fades, what cries laughs”) [4, p.69], the oppositional pairs “aç–sol” (bloom–fade) and “ağla–gül” (cry–laugh) illustrate the transient and changeable nature of life.

In “Dost başa bakar, düşman ayağa” (“A friend looks at the head, an enemy at the feet”) [4, p.158], the oppositions “dost–düşman” (friend–enemy) and “baş–ayaq” (head–feet) present contrasting models of perception and attitude. Here, the different perspectives of friends and enemies toward the same person are expressed in a figurative and contrastive manner.

In some paremiological units, antonyms also function to characterize different aspects of the same subject or phenomenon. In the proverb “Axsaq qoyuna nə dağ, nə aran” (“For a lame sheep, neither mountains nor lowlands are suitable”) [2, p.86], the antonyms “dağ” (mountain) and “aran” (lowland/plain) create a spatial opposition. In “Bəy ilə dost olanın tövləsi dolu olar, samanlığı boş” (“One who befriends a bey has a full stable, but an empty barn”) [2, p.114], the antonyms “dolu” (full) and “boş” (empty) express the inconsistency between outward prosperity and internal deficiency.

In conclusion, it can be stated that in Turkish and Azerbaijani paremiological units antonyms carry significant semantic and stylistic functional load. In proverbs, they are not limited to expressing opposition, but also expand the possibilities of comparison, generalization, enumeration, and figurative expression, thereby enhancing the semantic depth of the text. The analysis shows that the syntactic positioning of antonyms is one of the key factors determining the intensity of contrast and expressive effect. At the same time, some antonymic pairs become stabilized in context, partially weakening their original oppositional semantics and turning into generalized semantic units. A comparative approach further reveals that, although similar functional models are observed in the paremiological systems of both languages, their forms of expression are realized through different imagery and structural features depending on the national and cultural context. In this regard, antonyms function as one of the key lexical-semantic means that both expand the stylistic potential of the language and reflect the worldview of the people.

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